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ACCUMULATION OF LEAD IN MOLLUSCS MERETRIX LYRATA IN THE ESTUARY PART OF VIETNAM

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Annotation: Due to their immobility and accumulation of biological substances Molluscs are commonly used as biomarkers in studies of waste chemical accumulation in the estuary part of Bach Dang River (Viet Nam). This research aims to investigate the accumulation of lead in Meretrix Lyrata molloscs in the Bach Dang River. Lead concentrations in the stomach are shown to be three times higher than the lead concentrations in the meat of the mollusc. The accumulation of lead into the stomach is shown to be related to their diet while the accumulation of lead in the stomach is connected with their nutrition and lipid content.

Keywords: molluscs, Meretrix Lyrata, lead, estuary part of Bach Dang River

НАКОПЛЕНИЕ СВИНЦА В МОЛЛЮСКАХ MERETRIX LYRATA В ЭСТУАРНОЙ ЧАСТИ ВЬЕТНАМА

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Аннотация: Из-за своей неподвижности и накопления биологических веществ моллюски обычно используются в качестве биомаркеров в исследованиях накопления химических отходов в эстуарной части реки Бахданг (Вьетнам). Целью данного исследования является изучение накопления свинца в моллюсках Meretrix Lyrata в реке Бахданг. Показано, что концентрация свинца в желудке в три раза превышает концентрацию свинца в мясе моллюска. Показано, что накопление свинца в желудке связано с их

рационом, в то время как накопление свинца в желудке связано с их питанием и содержанием липидов.

Ключевые слова: моллюски, *Meretrix Lyrata*, свинец, эстуарная часть реки Бахданг

Introduction

It is generally believed that, the more developed society and the faster industrialization, the more toxic wastes are released into the. Leakage of toxic substances may occur from the production activity or during transportation and storage of substances in warehouses. The release of various chemical pollutants such as Cu, Hg, Cd from landfills, agricultural production and excessive exploitation of natural resources causes more and more damage to the biosphere every day. The bioaccumulation of these toxins along the food chain leads to harmful effects on all living organisms, including humans

Bioaccumulation is a process in which living organisms accumulate chemical substances directly from the environment and from sources of nutrition. Chemicals from the environment are first absorbed through pleura, gills, and intestines of the organisms due to the process of passive diffusion. Chemicals must penetrate the lipid layer of the pleura to enter the body, therefore the potential for the bioaccumulation of chemical substances is associated with the possibility of dissolution of these substances. In the aquatic environment, toxic substances that have an affinity with lipids penetrate through the barrier between the natural environment and the living organism. Since rivers, lakes, and oceans contain sediments of the toxic substances, and aquatic organisms allow a large amount of water to pass through their respiratory system, a certain amount of chemicals get into their bodies out of the water. Therefore, aquatic organisms can accumulate chemicals in concentrations exceeding their content in the environment. High concentrations of toxic substances in meat and organs of aquatic organisms can pose a threat to human health when consumed.

The estuary area of the Bach Dang River has the characteristic features of a river region with a tropical climate. It has high biological diversity and rich aquatic resources. With plentiful food sources, limestone,

coral reefs, and calcium supply sources, beaches in the tidal zone are favorable for the breeding of *Meretrix Lyrata* [1-4].

In the estuary area of the Bach Dang River receives large amount of pollution from different sources, such as port activities, water transport, ship building and repairing, old ship-breaking, offshore industrial zones, agricultural, and household sources contribute to the pollution of this river. Toxins accumulate in the living organisms inhabiting the estuary of the Bach Dang River, among which is the popular *Meretrix Lyrata* species. Due to its strong toxicity and high bioaccumulation potential, lead is a particularly important toxin to investigate [1-4].

Bivalve molluscs, living on the seabed in the marine coastal zone, have become the objects of much research because of their high predisposition to bioaccumulation, sedentary lifestyle, and the organic sediments they eat. They pose a danger to human health when consumed as food, if too much toxins (such as heavy metals and hardly decomposable organic matter) have accumulated in their meat and shellfish organs. As of 2017, most developed countries have introduced Standards for Safe Consumption of seafood and shellfish. Since 2007 the aquaculture industry in Vietnam has grows rapidly as Vietnam became the 150th member of the World Trade Organization (WTO) opening up prospects for the export of agricultural products, especially seafood. The bivalve molluscs is among the most popular seafood in the world market.

Currently, there has been little research on the mechanism of lead accumulation in the meat of living organisms in particular the molluscs *Meretrix Lyrata* in the estuary of the Bach Dang Rive. Previous studies have mainly characterized the current state of contamination by heavy metals. The process of accumulation as the organism grows has not been investigated. Previous research concentrated only on laboratory analysis and the use of the mathematical model of interpolation. The content of lead in the environment and in the meat of *Meretrix Lyrata* in the estuary of the Bach Dang River has not been studied.

For the analysis of lead, the method of quantitative analysis and an atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) were used. Heavy metal concentrations are expressed as milligrams per kilogram (mg/kg) of wet weight for the mollusc's samples. Heavy metal concentration in the water is expressed as milligrams per liter (mg/l). An independent t-test analysis was applied to the observed data to check the level of significance site-wise.

The data was processed with a statistical method, the average values were compared using a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and LSD with $\alpha = 0.05$ was tested.

Lead contaminated food enters the siphon, and then into the gills of *Meretrix Lyrata*. Gills consist of wide gill plates. They simultaneously perform respiratory function and filter food from water. Two parts of the gills (plates) are located on both sides of the body, their ends are around the mouth, and they supply food directly into the mouth. A large gill system filters the food from the water, then moves it to the tentacles that are located around the mouth, the food is crushed and moves into the mouth. *Meretrix Lyrata* can select and filter food from water, they mix it with mucus and push into the mouth, and then the wastes are removed from the body in the form of "pseudofaeces".

According to the obtained results, lead is present in the natural environment of the breeding of molluscs in all the components, i.e. in water, dry residue and bottom sediments. Lead in bottom sediments can be in different chemical states (tabl. 1), generally in immobile form.

Table 1 – Forms of lead in bottom sediments

Metal	General concentration of lead		Carbon		Oxide Fe-Mn		Organics		Other states	
	mg/kg	%	mg/kg	%	mg/kg	%	mg/kg	%	mg/kg	%
Pb	14.48	100	-	0.00	4.40	30.39	5.88	40.61	4.20	29.00

Lead in a state of organic matter exists in humus (mainly, humic and fulvic acids), which is also a source of food for molluscs, and in this form lead can be accumulated in their organisms. The results of the analysis of the samples of the bottom sediments, taken from different places on the beach, showed that their concentration of lead is not different, the even distribution of lead on the beach for a natural breeding of molluscs is clearly seen, and there is no localization of contamination.

Since the concentration of dissolved lead in water is very small – on average 0.003 mg/kg, it can be concluded that the movement of lead from the beach mud for the breeding of molluscs into the water is insignificant. This conclusion is necessary for further study of the patterns

of lead accumulation in the body of *Meretrix lyrata* in the estuary area of the Bach Dang River that will develop recommendations for the safe use of *Meretrix lyrata* in food.

According to the obtained results, it is evident that the lead content in the meat of the individuals under study increases with their growth. In other words, the content of lead in the meat of *Meretrix Lyrata* is proportional to their size and age. Figure 1 shows the correlation between age and lead content in *Meretrix Lyrata* meat (fig. 1).

Figure 1 – Correlation between age and lead content in meat of *Meretrix Lyrata*

The correlation coefficient between lead content in *Meretrix Lyrata* and age expresses a close positive relationship between the two factors $R^2 = 0.96$, $r = 0.97$, $p < 0.01$. According to the results, *Meretrix Lyrata* can act as an environmental biomarker. In addition, there are other factors that influence the possibility of accumulation of lead in *Meretrix Lyrata* from the environment, which were estimated through the correlation coefficient in CORREL.

Table 2 – Coefficient of correlation between factors of the environment and lead content in meat of *Meretrix Lyrata*

Permanent factors	Content Pb in <i>Meretrix Lyrata</i>
TSS	-0,35
Lipid	0,88

Permanent factors	Content Pb in Meretrix Lyrata
Salinity	0,51
Dissolved oxygen	0,58
pH	0,24
Temperature	-0,42
Pb	-0,38
Age	0,97

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